

Crime against Senior Citizens and Legal Protection in India

Pratiksha Dwivedi¹ Dr. Abhimanyu Sethy²

¹LLM 3rd Semester Tezpur University, Assam

²Faculty Madhusudan Law University

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Abstract

In India, crimes against the senior citizen have been increasing rapidly. Today, they are mostly the victims of various crimes like murder, serious injuries, cheating and brutality and they are unattainable to other family members and neighbours due to lack of neighbourhood involvement, dependence on others, family violence, vulnerability, defensibility etc. These incidents attract the academicians as well as the policy makers to pay notice to the various dimensions of these crimes. There is a higher danger to the life of the senior citizens in our nation. The senior citizens have not been tossed out of the standard as far as possible however they are left without any assets and are seen powerless in their homes. Movement, urbanization, industrialization and globalization has obsessed scrambling of space in the urban communities, in this manner the senior citizen are abandoned by their little youngsters so they can keep up their ideal ways of life. Crime against the senior citizen such as murder, financial crimes, fraud, and burglary are the most common. Criminals consider the elderly people as easy targets because they are physically fragile and they are less able to shield or care for themselves. The senior citizens are considered as the bastions of our nation. They most likely won't be a lot of dynamic like they were in their young age, however their experience of life is momentous of the current ages on the grounds that our seniors have seen the best and the most noticeably unpleasant of both conformist and present day world.

Key words: legal, senior, crime, citizens and protection.

Introduction

Ageing is an inevitable process that attracts different types of disabilities and dependencies that necessitate the requirement of enacting specific categories of laws, rules and regulations to protect the rights of elderly persons. Laws primarily tend to protect the elderly persons from several types of 'elderly abuse' which are manifest in our society in several forms such as-neglect or permanent abandonment, physically abusing the elderly as they are easy to target psychological abuse as they desire more care and attention, verbal abuse, financial abuse, healthcare abuse etc. The definition of elderly persons primarily comprises those persons whose age almost surpasses the average life span of human beings. But it's difficult to define its boundary exactly as every society has its meaning. According to the 'National Policy on the elderly person, 1999' elderly person means a person who has attained the age of sixty years or above. In earlier times, the elderly enjoyed a significant position in the family. The elder member of the family was considered the head of the family, and all the other members followed the decisions and orders taken by the head. The present research work primarily focuses on the causes and impact of various abuses against the elderly persons, existing legislative framework and the response of judiciary. This paper refers the doctrinal study with constitutional provision, statutory enactments and judicial decisions regarding the care and protection of senior citizens in India.

Causes of crimes against the Senior Citizen

Growing old is natural, and changes occur in a person's physical and mental well-being. This gives prominence to the loss of earning opportunities and capacities, eventually resulting in dependence on the family members for survival and basic needs. The family starts treating the older persons as a burden and considers them not in a position to contribute in any aspect. Ageing and its related problems are diverse and need a more comprehensive approach. Elderly persons are considered a vulnerable section of society as they are easy targets. The number of elderly abuse reported by the National Crime Records Bureau since 2014 is debilitating. As per the NCRB 2020, Delhi had the highest number of crimes committed against senior citizens, and it reported about 906 crimes committed against them in 2020. The crime against elderly persons is one of such grey areas which, despite several enactments and legal provisions of far-reaching significance, did not receive the deserved attention or required response. The most important cause of the crimes committed against the senior citizens is the transition of nuclear family from the earlier prevailing joint family structure as with this the elderly people are staying alone for most of the time and with this multiple opportunity is created for committing crimes against the elderly persons. Apart from this there could be several other factors responsible such as urbanisation, industrialization and globalization due to which we often see how the elderly persons are left alone. The prominent reason why the elderly population are often targeted is that due to

deteriorating health conditions and there dependencies which creates a need for them to depend on other persons even for carrying out the minor day to day activities. And when we are dependent on someone it is obvious that the other person is in a convenient position to exercise undue influence. The elderly persons are in a need of constant care, attention and affection and what they get is abandonment, neglect and several other forms of abuse. People often misbehave with the elderly persons as they consider them to be a responsibility and those persons who are not in a position to contribute them. Industrialisation and Urbanization has also contributed to the rise in the number of offences against the senior citizens. Due to this the younger generation is found migrating to the metropolitan cities for pursuing their education or pursuing their carrier and being established in their professional carrier and in this process we often find the parents i.e. the elderly population left behind alone and lonely which makes their status more vulnerable. The sudden shift to modern society and shift to the world of digitalisation and virtual space the elderly population has generally been considered not to be the suitable part as they would not be in a position to contribute or be a part of the developing system.

The status of an elderly person basically depends on the way how the society and most importantly their family treat them. If their family considers them to be an integral part and gives them all the required attention, care and love then the society will also have a respectful attitude towards those elderly persons. The elderly has witnessed such a significant position in the family in the ancient history but with modernisation and influence of various factors changes the approaches towards the elderly.

Legislative framework towards senior citizen The constitution of India

Constitution of India strives to create a free society, through justice in all sphere of life, irrespective of the caste, sex, race, religion, creed or age. The Preamble of the Constitution secures to all its citizens, certain rights and standards. Social justice is possible only when there survive a society for all ages. Economic justice mandates the prospect to the older persons to secure an adequate means of livelihood or financial independence. Liberty is associated to the dignity and independence of the older persons. The expression of senior citizen should not to be sabotaged by the younger generation, and the faith and worship be held by the elderly are to be respected and allowed. Equally status and

opportunity is very important for the older persons. The Preamble of the constitution along with Article 51 (c) which mandates the State to make an effort to promote respect for international law and treaty obligations. The International Plan of Action on Ageing, 2002 “to make certain that senior citizen are able to age with security and dignity and to continue to participate in their societies with full rights” and thereby create “a society for all ages”.

Personal laws:

Hindu law

The Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956 authorises a person to look after the needs of his parents who are not in a position to carry out their expenses under sec. 20. The elderly persons should not be left in a state of isolation in the streets or asking for help here and there. Initially it was the duty of the son to maintain his aged parents but now, it is also the duty of the daughter to maintain her elderly parents who are not in a position to maintain them. In the case of *K.M. Adam Vs. Gopalkrishnan*, 1974, the Supreme Court declared that if the child is a Hindu, it is obligatory for him to maintain his parents irrespective of the fact whether the father or mother is Hindu or not.

Muslim law

Under Islam it is significant for every person to carry out the expenses of his father and mother, who are not in a position to carry out their own expenses as per Mulla. Under the Hanafi Law, there is a duty cast upon the children to look after the needs of their parents and even the grandparents as per Tyabji. In Islam there is no law regulating the conduct of the children to maintain their parents but those practice Islam it automatically applies upon them.

The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973

The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 under Section 125 authorities that as and when the matter arises the Magistrate may pass an order directing the children including the married daughters to carry out the expenses of their old parents.

Maintenance and welfare of parents and senior citizens act 2007

Giving accent for the need of a central legislation on the point of maintenance of the Senior citizens the Parliament of India enacted the 'Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007 in the year 2007. The Act casts a duty upon the children to look after the necessities of their parents. As per the Act it is necessary that the State Governments establishes one or more tribunals for looking into the matters

related to the maintenance of the elderly persons. The maximum amount which could be awarded by the tribunal is 10,000 and the maximum imprisonment is for a period of three months. The Tribunal is also competent to award a fine of 5000 instead of imprisonment or it may award both. Under Section 5 of the said Act, a senior citizen who is unable to maintain him or herself can make an application against their children to carry out their expenses. Any senior citizen not having children of their own can make an application against those relatives mentioned in the Act. The Act requires the State Governments to establish and keep up a suitable number of old age home with all the required facilities. The State Governments should begin with having at least one old age home in every district for the initial period and the number may increase as and when the necessity arises.

The Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens (Amendments) Bill 2019

The Central government proposed a draft bill in 2019 to amend the provisions of the act with the objective of ensuring need based maintenance based and senior citizens and their welfare. In 2019 the Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens (Amendment) Bill, 2019 was introduced by the centre in the Lok Sabha. The basic objective of the bill was to increase the scope of the definition of children and include even the adopted sons and daughters, step children, son in law and daughter in law, grandson and granddaughter. The parents would also cover on both biological and adoptive parents and most vitally as father-in-law and mother-in-law. The maintenance has extended and suggests to be providing in such a manner, that they can lead a life of respect and dignity. The Bill recommends that the children should pay the amount within 15 days of passing of the order and not within 30 days as per the 2007 Act. The Bills recommends of increasing the imprisonment to six months and even increase the fine to 10,000.

Judicial pronouncements towards elderly persons

Justice is the balancing of interest between two aggrieved parties. The Justice system prevailing in the country always proves to be the most efficient in rendering speedy and effective justice to the people of India especially for the elderly persons who forms the significant part of the nation. The evident portion is that the apex court is always aware of the fact that elderly persons need a special care and attention so that they could live a life of dignity and respect and be able to enjoy all the rights and liberties meted out

to them. The Supreme Court and the various High Courts are already aware of the increase in the number of elder abuses in the country.

According to the World Health Organization, in spite of the rise in the number of cases relating to elderly abuse in India we find very few case law on the issue of elderly abuse as often we see that the decisions passed by the Courts in this aspect are not published under the category of elderly abuse. A prominent reason why we don't have sufficient number of case laws is that most incidents are never placed in the Judicial System in the first instance.

The atrocities meted out to the elderly persons may be difficult to prove. The availability of the physical evidence may be next to impossible because of the delay in reporting of the cases or because of the failure to identify that atrocity has been committed. Witnesses may not be ready and willing to come to the court and give their statement. Moreover in many cases we have seen that the victim is unable to testify either because of the delay in the matter reaching the stage of decision or his condition at the time of the abuse was such that he was not in a position to identify the victim. In the matters related to the elderly abuse, the courts can play an important role in providing the elderly persons from the different forms of abuse, compensating them for damages, enabling them to cope up with the financial losses they have incurred and prosecuting the aggressors. The elderly persons we often see are not in favour of bringing criminal actions against their own family members, care givers, dependents, neighbours or any person in a fiduciary capacity. Reasons could be multiple like fear of more abuse, no intention of putting the abuser in more trouble, dependency on the abuser and anticipation of being shifted to a nursing home. Moreover many a times the victim is not aware that he or she is experiencing any form of elderly abuse and that there could be a remedy to get relief. Despite of the difficulties cited above it is seen that many cases related to elderly abuse are not only reported but the Supreme Court has also granted justice to such victims. The Hon'ble Chief Justice of India has advised Chief Justices of all the High Courts in India to pay special attention to the cases concerning the Elderly persons and try to resolve the matters in an expeditious manner in the Year 1999 itself in accordance with the Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment New Delhi.

Case laws

Certain leading case laws have been discussed on issues of care and maintenance of senior citizen

in our country. In case of Bhagwan Dutt Vs. Kamla Devi, the court had discussed the object of Section 125 Cr.P.C. which is to protect the dependents from vagrancy and need. It is the moral duty of every son or daughter to maintain, support or take care of their parents. When the son or daughter is capable of providing maintenance it would be unjust that the parents are left alone on the streets. In case Santosh Surendra Patil Vs. Surendra Narasgopnda Patil, 2017 the Court has advised and recommended the State Governments to act as guardians of senior citizens and old infirmed parents who are left alone in the streets with no one to look after being subjected to the various forms of elderly abuse. In case of Kirtikant D. Vadodaria Vs. State of Gujarat, 1996 SC held that the elderly parents are entitled to get maintenance from their daughter just as they are entitled to receive from their son under the Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956.

In the case of Jharkhand Senior Citizens Advocates service Sansthan and Another Vs. State of Jharkhand , 2016 the High Court of Jharkhand held that the State Government should as soon as possible setup Old Age Homes in each district for the victims of elderly abuse and the helpless and homeless elderly persons. The State should also make necessary arrangements in the hospitals for the treatment of the elderly persons so that they should be treated as soon as possible.

Conclusion

Old age is not a “disaster” that affects only people on the other side of the globe. It is an unavoidable side of everyone’s life. As a person advances in age, due to physiological and psychological incapacities that may develop with old age, he/she may need support from family and community for dignified nourishment. Deteriorate of the traditional family support systems has destroyed and older persons being left alone to sustain for them. This results in violation of the priceless human rights, of the older persons including rights to security, participation, health care, adequate standard of living, freedom from torture or cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment and dignity. The central government have enacted certain laws and policies to protect the senior citizens from certain kinds of cruelty and abuse. The judiciary also stands on care and protection of senior citizens in India.

Suggestion

The problem of the senior citizens should be addressed to urgently and with maximum care. There is urgent need to amend the Constitution for the special provision to protection of the senior citizen and bring it in the margin of fundamental right. The degeneration of joint family system, disruption of familiar bonds and loss of respect for the aged person, the family in modern times should not be thought to be a secure place for them. Thus, it should be the Constitutional duty of the State to make an Act for the welfare and extra protection of the senior citizen including sedative care.

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